

Wind inflow observation from load harmonics via neural networks: A simulation and field study

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Wind estimation
Wind sensing
Wind shears
Wind misalignments
Machine learning
Neural networks

ABSTRACT

In this work, feed-forward neural networks are used to estimate the inflow of a wind turbine in real time during operation. A previously published method achieved this capability by correlating the turbine response to the wind inflow via a piecewise-linear model. Specifically, the existing formulation used the once-per-revolution harmonics of both in- and out-of-plane blade bending moments to estimate four wind parameters: the vertical and horizontal shears, and the vertical and horizontal misalignment angles. The novel method presented here builds on the same concept, but replaces the linear model with neural networks. Compared to the previous approach, the neural-based one is simpler to tune and use, because it decouples the wind parameters, which can be observed each one independently from the others.

The proposed formulation is tested using both aeroservoelastic simulations and field data obtained on a 3.5 MW machine. In the field, independent measurements of the inflow are provided by a nearby hub-tall met mast, providing data for the training and verification of the wind observer. Notwithstanding some limitations of the experimental setup, results indicate that the neural networks produce estimates of the shears and yaw misalignment angle with accuracies compatible with typical use cases in wind turbine and wind farm control. Additionally, the neural-based observer appears to slightly outperform the original formulation in the lower wind speed range, where stronger nonlinearities in the load-wind mapping can occur.

1. Introduction

With the exception of some prototypes or instrumented machines for experimental or certification tests, most turbine installations are rather oblivious of their wind surroundings. In fact, today's on-board anemometry is installed on the nacelle or the spinner, and can only provide wind speed and direction at that location. These are point-wise (in contrast to rotor-equivalent) measurements, and blind to shears — both in the case of ambient flow shears and of those caused by wake impingement. Some sites are equipped with met masts, which carry multiple measuring instruments including anemometers and wind vanes at different heights above ground, thereby providing information on the vertical wind speed gradient. However, a met tower is not co-located with the rotors of the turbines in a farm, and therefore is blind to any flow heterogeneity; additionally, masts often reach only up to hub height. Remote sensing devices such as lidars and radars [1–7] are able to scan the wind field, providing temporal maps of the flow at locations of interest. However, production turbines and farms are today not routinely equipped with such devices, which are often deployed only for characterization and test campaigns.

In summary, today's turbines and wind plants operate only based on a somewhat limited knowledge of the flow in which they are immersed. This gap provides the main motivation for *wind sensing*, a technology where the whole rotor is used as a wind measurement device.

Wind sensing refers to the general concept of using the response of the turbine to estimate characteristics of the inflow, a task that can be accomplished in several different ways. A first example of wind sensing is the well-known idea of estimating the rotor-effective wind speed via the torque balance equation from measured power or torque, a method now in widespread use by industry [8–11].

Generalizing this concept, *wind observers* have been proposed to estimate not only speed but also shears via blade loads [11–13]. For example, the approach of Schreiber et al. [11] mirrors the torque-balance estimator, but uses out-of-plane blade bending instead of power/torque. The idea is simple but quite powerful: when a blade is instrumented with load measuring devices, it can be used as a scanning sensor. This way, in its travel around the rotor disk, each blade produces local speed measurements, which can then be used to reconstruct shears. When the turbine is already equipped with load sensors, for example to

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support load-reducing control and/or condition monitoring functions, wind sensing is a new capability that does not require extra hardware, in contrast to other flow-measurement solutions.

Another wind sensing approach was proposed first by Bottasso and Riboldi [14] and then further developed by Bottasso and Riboldi [15], Cacciola et al. [16], Bertelè et al. [17,18,19,20] and Bertelè and Bottasso [21,22]. Using this technique, the observation of wind characteristics is still obtained from the rotor response in the form of blade loads; however, in this case the observer, instead of using directly the load time histories, is formulated in terms of their once-per-revolution (1P) harmonics. Indeed, Bottasso and Riboldi [14] first showed that both the vertical shear of the inflow and the lateral misalignment of the rotor axis with the wind vector leave a specific trace in the 1P harmonic of the blade response, and that such a mark can be inverted; in other words, if the response is measured, the vertical shear and the misalignment angle that produced that response can be computed. The method was subsequently expanded to estimate also the horizontal shear and the vertical misalignment (or upflow) angle [16]. The observation model is based on an assumed parametric relationship between four *wind parameters* (two shears and two angles, here also referred to as *wind states*) and in- and out-of-plane 1P load harmonics. After the free model parameters are tuned, wind estimates are computed at run time based on measured loads using least squares or by Kalman filtering [22].

All these wind observers are based on the inversion of the relationship between the wind inflow and the response that it generates on the turbine in terms of blade loads. Different wind turbine types will respond in different ways to the same wind inflow input. Hence these observers are type-specific, and need to be tuned for each turbine model on which they are installed. However, they are probably not pad-specific, because the response of a turbine to a given wind input depends on its aero-structural design and control system, not on where it is located nor on what produced that wind input. Although this appears to be a reasonable assumption, it has not yet been demonstrated experimentally in the field and remains an open point for future research.

Notwithstanding some promising initial field validation results [20], there are aspects of the harmonic observer that can be improved. One first limiting factor of the existing formulation is the assumed model structure. In fact, to retain a linear mapping between wind parameters and load harmonics, the formulation is based on an assumed degree of nonlinearity [17]; this method, however, leads to a large number of parameters above a quadratic functional dependency. This problem was addressed by using a linear model around preselected mean speed values, resulting in a piecewise-linear wind-scheduled load-wind map. Although a piecewise-linear dependency has typically proven to be adequate in most cases studied so far, a more general formulation is desirable. A second and more significant limitation of the existing formulation is that the identification of the load-wind model requires simultaneous measurements of the four wind parameters. This problem can be relaxed by exploiting the rotational symmetry of the rotor [19]: in a nutshell, this means that the response to a given horizontal wind misalignment is the same as the response to a same vertical misalignment, but azimuthally shifted by a quarter of a revolution. The same holds also for the horizontal and vertical shears. However, even in this case one still needs to simultaneously measure at least two wind parameters, namely one angle and one shear. This proved to be a limiting factor in the validation work attempted in Bertelè et al. [20]: there, the met mast was equipped with multiple wind speed measurements above ground (thereby providing a reference shear for training), but had only one wind vane at hub height. This pointwise measurement is not an ideal reference for training an observer that should estimate a rotor-equivalent quantity; additionally, possible inaccuracies in the measurement of wind direction might pollute the estimates of the shear, and viceversa, due to the coupled nature of the estimation procedure.

Goal of this work is to overcome these limitations of the existing harmonic-based formulation. Here, a feed-forward neural network (NN) is used to represent the load-wind model. NNs are universal approximators, in the sense that they are theoretically capable of approximating any measurable function to any desired degree of accuracy [23]; hence, high-order nonlinearities can be readily taken into account, as necessary. Additionally, the problem can be formulated in such a way that each wind parameter is estimated by a separate network. This way, dedicated observers can be developed only for the quantities for which reliable references are available, and there is no possible cross-contamination due to poor quality measures.

Other authors have used machine learning methods to estimate wind conditions. For example, Wang et al. [24] developed a method to estimate wind speed, whereas Mirabilli and Habets [25] and Jiang [26] were able to estimate both speed and horizontal direction by using microphones and ocean wave spectra. García-Gutiérrez et al. [27] used lidar measurements to train a network and estimate wind speed, vertical profile and wind direction. However, the present work remains – to the authors' knowledge – the first method based on neural networks that is capable of simultaneously estimating shears and directions, during operation, directly at the rotor disk, and based on measurements (SCADA data and blade loads) that are often already available on modern wind turbines to support other purposes, thereby resulting in a particularly simple and low cost solution.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the overall methodology, including a brief description of the original harmonic-based observer, and the new formulation based on a neural network architecture. In Section 3, the proposed formulation is tested in a synthetic environment and using field data, and compared to the original implementation. Finally, Section 4 presents and discusses the main findings of this study.

2. Methods

2.1. Wind parameterization

The wind field is described in terms of the components u , v and w respectively along the \vec{x} , \vec{y} and \vec{z} axes of a hub-centered reference frame (see Fig. 1). The \vec{x} axis is parallel to the rotor rotation axis (and therefore might be inclined with respect to the ground if the rotor has an uptilt), \vec{y} is horizontal with respect to the ground and points to the left when looking downstream, while \vec{z} completes a right-handed triad. Non-dimensional coordinates along the three axes are respectively noted $\bar{x} = x/R$, $\bar{y} = y/R$, and $\bar{z} = z/R$, where R is the rotor radius.

The three components of the velocity vector are expressed as

$$u(\bar{y}, \bar{z}) = u_H + u_s(\bar{y}, \bar{z}), \quad (1a)$$

$$v(\bar{z}) = v_H + v_{vv}(\bar{z}), \quad (1b)$$

$$w(\bar{y}) = w_H + w_{hv}(\bar{y}). \quad (1c)$$

The subscript $(\cdot)_H$ indicates hub-height values. The term $u_s(\bar{y}, \bar{z})$ is the shear, and represents the spatial variability of the longitudinal velocity component over the rotor disk area. The dependency on \bar{z} expresses the so called vertical shear, which is typically linked to atmospheric stability and surface roughness, whereas the dependency on \bar{y} is the horizontal shear, which can be due to orographic features of the terrain and/or the presence of a wake released by an upstream wind turbine. The horizontal cross flow velocity component is v , where $v_{vv}(\bar{z})$ is the vertical veer, caused by the interaction between Coriolis and frictional forces in the boundary layer as described by the Ekman spiral [28]. Vertical veer is typically strongly correlated with vertical shear, and is often observed in night-time stable atmospheric conditions [29]. The vertical cross flow velocity (or upflow) is noted w , and is typically caused by terrain features. The horizontal veer $w_{hv}(\bar{y})$ models the spatial variability of the upflow; this is typically small or negligible,

Fig. 1. Vertical (a) and horizontal (b) shears, cross-flows (c), and reference frame used for their definition (d).

and is introduced for completeness of the formulation. The three wind velocity components can be approximated by Taylor series (or other similar polynomial expansions [30]) as

$$u(\bar{y}, \bar{z}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_u} \sum_{j=0}^{N_u} u_{ij} \bar{y}^i \bar{z}^j, \quad (2a)$$

$$v(\bar{z}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_v} v_i \bar{z}^i, \quad (2b)$$

$$w(\bar{y}) = \sum_{i=0}^{N_w} w_i \bar{y}^i, \quad (2c)$$

where $u_0 = u_H$, $v_0 = v_H$, and $w_0 = w_H$. It is the goal of a wind observer to estimate the unknown coefficients u_{ij} , v_i , and w_i of these series expansions.

2.2. Effects of wind parameters on blade loads

The characteristics of the wind inflow determine the response of the rotor blades, including their internal loads. To formulate a wind observer based on measurements of these loads, it is useful to first understand the relationship between these quantities and the wind inflow that produces them. This wind-load relationship is typically highly complex and possibly non-linear, especially for the large, slender and flexible blades of modern wind turbines. As a consequence, the relationship has to be learnt from data, i.e. estimated using measurements of the wind input and the corresponding response. However, a simplified analytical analysis, although it cannot be accurate enough to have predictive capabilities, is still extremely useful to highlight the structure of the model.

The classical model of the flapwise and edgewise blade dynamics is used in various textbooks to explain the basic response of wind turbine rotors. The model derives the triangle of velocities at a generic blade cross section, which readily yields its angle of attack and hence the aerodynamic sectional loads; integration along the blade span gives the bending moment. Following Eggleston and Stoddard [31], pag. 159, the contribution to the out-of-plane bending moment m^{OP} of a cross section at the radial distance r can be written with the present notation as

$$m^{OP} = m_0^{OP} + m_u^{OP} u_s(\bar{y}, \bar{z}) + m_v^{OP} v(\bar{z}) \cos \psi + m_w^{OP} w(\bar{y}) \sin \psi. \quad (3)$$

The coefficients m_u^{OP} , m_v^{OP} , and m_w^{OP} express the proportionality of the bending moment on shear and cross-flow components, whereas m_0^{OP}

does not depend on these effects. The azimuthal position of the blade is noted ψ , and $\psi = 0$ when the blade is vertical pointing downwards towards the terrain (see Fig. 1c). Hence, $\bar{y} = \bar{r} \sin \psi$ and $\bar{z} = -\bar{r} \cos \psi$, where $\bar{r} = r/R$. Inserting now the expansions expressed by Eqs. (2) into Eq. (3) gives the functional dependency of the flapping bending loads on the characteristics of the wind inflow:

$$m^{OP} = m_0^{OP} + m_u^{OP} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N_u} \sum_{j=0}^{N_u} u_{ij} (\bar{r} \sin \psi)^i (-\bar{r} \cos \psi)^j - u_{00} \right) + m_v^{OP} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N_v} v_i (-\bar{r} \cos \psi)^i \right) \cos \psi + m_w^{OP} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_w} w_i (\bar{r} \sin \psi)^i \right) \sin \psi. \quad (4)$$

This expression reveals two interesting aspects of the blade response. First, shears and cross-flows produce effects on blade loads at specific harmonics. Second, as the complexity of the inflow grows (or, in other words, for an increasing number of terms in the expansions of the inflow field), the response harmonics correspondingly increase in frequency. A similar analysis can be developed for the edgewise bending moment, leading to the same conclusions regarding its frequency content in relation to the inflow.

The simplest possible parameterization of the inflow is the choice $N_u = 1$, which represents linear vertical and horizontal shears, and $N_v = N_w = 0$, which corresponds to uniform lateral flow and upflow. With this choice, the response of the blade contains only the 1P sine and cosine harmonic components. This result is based on the assumption of linearity in the derivation of the model [31]; since this is not exactly true in reality, some higher harmonics will appear in the load spectrum, which are however small compared to the dominating 1P signal. The next term in the expansions adds a parabolic term to the shear, and a linear term to the cross flow, which represents the lowest order possible representation of veer. Using the properties of the powers of trigonometric functions [32], the response of the blade is found to contain now also the 2P sine and cosine harmonic components. The addition of each new term in the polynomial expansions of the three components increases the harmonics by one; for example, cubic shears and quadratic veers are associated with harmonics up to the 3P. Here again, because of non-linearities, there will be smaller effects at higher harmonics.

The present work uses the simplest possible parameterization of the inflow. This limits the blade harmonics to the single 1P, which is easy to compute even at relatively slow sampling rates. Intuitively, one should also probably expect a better repeatability of the lowest harmonics across different installations of a same wind turbine model. Additionally, since the actual load-wind map has to be learnt from data, the inclusion of higher order modes in the inflow requires the ability to measure these terms during the learning phase. The experimental dataset available for this work was collected with a simple set-up based on a hub-height met mast, which prevented more detailed measurements of the inflow. Further research and more sophisticated dataset are necessary to conclude whether the inclusion of higher order terms and harmonics can improve on the results shown here.

With the present simple choice, the wind components become

$$u(\bar{y}, \bar{z}) = u_H (1 + \kappa_v \bar{z} + \kappa_h \bar{y}), \quad (5a)$$

$$v(\bar{z}) = v_H, \quad (5b)$$

$$w(\bar{y}) = w_H, \quad (5c)$$

where $\kappa_v = u_{01}/u_H$ is the vertical linear shear coefficient, and $\kappa_h = u_{10}/u_H$ the horizontal linear shear coefficient. The lateral misalignment angle ϕ and the upflow angle χ (see Fig. 1d) are related to the three velocity components as

$$\bar{v} = \frac{v_H}{V_H} = \sin \phi \cos \chi, \quad (6a)$$

$$\tilde{w} = \frac{w_H}{V_H} = \sin \chi, \tag{6b}$$

where $V_H = \sqrt{u_H^2 + v_H^2 + w_H^2}$ is the wind speed resultant at the hub.

The parameters u_H , \tilde{v} , \tilde{w} , κ_v and κ_h are unknown, and should be estimated.

The hub-height longitudinal speed does not depend on load harmonics. It is estimated by the classical torque balance wind speed observer [10,11], which yields a rotor-equivalent value of this component that better reflects the average conditions at the rotor disk than the point-wise measurements provided by the on-board anemometry.

The remaining parameters depend on load harmonics, and are used to formulate the wind observer, as described next.

2.3. Wind observer formulations

The unknown wind parameters are collected in a vector θ , defined as $\theta = \{\tilde{v}, \kappa_v, \tilde{w}, \kappa_h\}^T$. The 1P harmonics of in- and out-plane bending loads are extracted via the Coleman–Feingold transformation [33] from the corresponding measured signals, then filtered and finally collected in vector $\mathbf{m} = \{m_{1c}^{OP}, m_{1s}^{OP}, m_{1c}^{IP}, m_{1s}^{IP}\}^T$. Subscripts $(\cdot)_{1s}$ and $(\cdot)_{1c}$ respectively indicate 1P sine and cosine harmonic amplitudes, while superscripts $(\cdot)^{OP}$ and $(\cdot)^{IP}$ the out- and in-plane load components, respectively.

Inspired by the results of the flapwise and edgewise blade model, for a given wind speed V and air density ρ a load-wind map $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ is assumed to link the load vector \mathbf{m} with the wind state vector θ , i.e.

$$\theta = \mathcal{M}(\mathbf{m}, V, \rho). \tag{7}$$

This way, when $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ is known, one can estimate the wind parameters θ by using measured \mathbf{m} , V , and ρ . The model implicitly assumes that the response of the turbine (including its closed-loop control system), and the resulting loading \mathbf{m} only depend on the ambient conditions θ , V and ρ . The dependency on wind speed V accounts for the different behavior, control and deformation of the machine in different operating conditions. In this work, this scheduling wind speed is computed as $V = f(u_E)$, where u_E is the rotor-equivalent estimate obtained by a wind speed observer [10], and $f(\cdot)$ is a 30-s moving average that removes fast fluctuations to smoothly follow the changes in operating conditions of the turbine. The dependency on air density ρ accounts for the aerodynamic origin of the loads. In this work, air density is obtained from ambient conditions as a function of temperature, pressure and humidity [34]. However, standards allow to neglect humidity, because it is rarely measured at a site and its influence on air density is small [35]. Individual pitch control can be used to alleviate periodic loads, including those that are used here to estimate the inflow; in this case, pitch harmonics are added to the load-wind model to increase observability [18].

The model assumes a steady-state response. Although this limits its ability to follow rapid transients, results indicate that it is capable of tracking the typical temporal scales of the inflow that are relevant for various possible use cases. These may range from the relatively fast effects on shear caused by wake meandering (time scales of the order of seconds), to wind direction changes relevant for yaw control (time scales of tens of seconds), to changes in atmospheric stability and its effects on shear (time scales of the order of tens of minutes/hours), which drive wake behavior and are relevant for wind farm control. To compensate for the lack of dynamics in the load-wind model, Bertelè and Bottasso [22] added a Kalman filter to the formulation, where the unknown wind parameters were augmented with their own dynamics, driven by a process noise term, resulting in an improved quality of the estimates. This refined formulation was not used in the present work to limit the complexity of the study, but could be readily applied to the new NN-based estimator.

Two ways of formulating $\mathcal{M}(\cdot)$ are considered in this work: the first inverts a piecewise-linear model, and is reviewed in Section 2.3.1, whereas the second uses neural networks, as proposed in Section 2.3.2.

2.3.1. Existing formulation

The previously published method (see Bertelè et al. [20] and references therein) assumes a relationship between wind states and rotor loads in the linear form

$$\mathbf{m} = \mathbf{F}(V, \rho)\theta + \mathbf{m}_0(V, \rho) = [\mathbf{F}(V, \rho) \ \mathbf{m}_0(V, \rho)] \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T}(V, \rho) \bar{\theta}. \tag{8}$$

This model is termed here and in the following *legacy model*. Matrix \mathbf{F} and vector \mathbf{m}_0 are the unknown model coefficients: \mathbf{F} collects the derivative of the moments with respect to the wind states, while \mathbf{m}_0 represents gravity-induced loads.

The gravitational term hides a difficulty of the present method, because \mathbf{m}_0 is made up by two contributions: (a) a constant one, which depends on the undeformed shape of the turbine (for example, up tilt generates an out-of-plane bending moment on the blades); and (b) a variable contribution due to aeroelastic deformations (for example, thrust bends the blades, in turn modifying their gravity-induced bending). Given that only the latter term depends on density, these moment contributions need to be decoupled in order to correct the model expressed by (8) for density variations. The interested reader is referred to [20] for details.

Interestingly, the model coefficients \mathbf{F} are not all independent. Indeed, neglecting tower-induced disturbances, the axial symmetry of the rotor implies that the effect of an horizontal shear is the same as the one of a vertical shear of the same entity, simply shifted by $\pi/2$. The same holds for the relative angles between wind vector and rotor axis: the effect of a lateral misalignment is the same caused by a vertical misalignment of a same entity, but shifted by a quarter of a revolution. This *rotational symmetry* of the rotor behavior [19] not only decreases the number of unknowns, but also eases the identification of the model. In fact, to create the load-wind map one does not need to measure all four wind parameters but only two: one angle and one shear. This is advantageous, especially in the field, where all wind parameters might not be readily measurable.

Dropping the dependency on V and ρ for notational simplicity, the model coefficients \mathbf{T} are identified by stacking side by side N wind state measurements θ into a matrix $\Theta = [\bar{\theta}_1, \dots, \bar{\theta}_N]$, while the corresponding measured blade loads \mathbf{m} are stacked into matrix $\mathbf{M} = [\mathbf{m}_1, \dots, \mathbf{m}_N]$, obtaining

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{T}\Theta. \tag{9}$$

The model coefficients are then computed by least squares as

$$\mathbf{T} = \mathbf{M}\Theta^T (\Theta\Theta^T)^{-1}. \tag{10}$$

Measured loads \mathbf{m}_M are defined as

$$\mathbf{m}_M = \mathbf{m} + \mathbf{r}, \tag{11}$$

where \mathbf{m} is given by Eq. (8) and \mathbf{r} is the residual with covariance \mathbf{Q} :

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{r}\mathbf{r}^T]. \tag{12}$$

Residuals are assumed to be zero-mean and colored, and are due to measurement noise and unmodeled physics [36]. Given the model coefficients, a maximum likelihood [37] estimate θ_E of the wind states is computed online during turbine operation from the measured loads \mathbf{m}_M from Eqs. (8) and (11) as follows

$$\theta_E = (\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{Q}^{-1} \mathbf{F})^{-1} \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{Q}^{-1} (\mathbf{m}_M - \mathbf{m}_0). \tag{13}$$

The problem is solved iteratively: first an initial covariance is guessed; then, once an estimate has been obtained, the covariance is updated from the residuals using Eq. (12); next, the problem is solved again. During online estimation, at each new time step the guess is taken as the value from the previous step, and the procedure typically converges in one single iteration. An alternative formulation, not used here, uses a Kalman Filter to estimate the wind states [22].

As shown by Eq. (13), in order to estimate the wind parameters one needs to successfully invert model (8). This is indeed possible since

matrix $F^T Q^{-1} F$ is non-singular [17]. However, the model inversion carries with it a significant limitation: the impossibility of decoupling the four wind states and to create independent observers.

2.3.2. Novel neural network formulation

To overcome some of the limitations of the legacy formulation, a new approach is proposed here based on a neural approximation of the load-wind map, which is written in this case as

$$\theta_E = NN(x_M), \tag{14}$$

where θ_E is one of the wind states (either \bar{v} , κ_v , \bar{w} , or κ_h), $NN(\cdot)$ is a static neural network function, $\mathbf{x} = \{\mathbf{m}^T, V, \rho\}^T$ is the vector of network inputs, while $(\cdot)_E$ and $(\cdot)_M$ respectively indicate estimated and measured quantities. The neural network function writes

$$NN(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{W}^T \sigma(\mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{a}) + \mathbf{b}, \tag{15}$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a vector of sigmoid activation functions, and the free model parameters are stored in vector $\mathbf{p} = \{\dots, W_{ij}, \dots, V_{ij}, \dots, a_i, \dots, b_i, \dots\}^T$, which collects the synaptic weights and biases of the network. A single-hidden-layer feedforward network structure is adopted, where the hidden layer is characterized by M neurons connected to the network inputs and outputs by the interconnection weights \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} , respectively [38].

Fig. 2 gives a schematic representation of the network architecture. Coherently with Eq. (14), there is one dedicated single-hidden layer network for each one of the wind states \bar{v} , κ_v , \bar{w} , and κ_h . Each network is fed by measured load harmonics $\mathbf{m} = \{m_{1c}^{OP}, m_{1s}^{OP}, m_{1c}^{IP}, m_{1s}^{IP}\}^T$. Additionally, since the response of the turbine depends on the operating and ambient conditions, also the wind speed V and air density ρ are provided as inputs. The speed V is computed as for the legacy model, and even here it is used as a scheduling parameter that accounts for the operating condition of the turbine. Density is used because aerodynamic loads depend on it. However, differently from the legacy model, in this black-box approach it is not necessary to eliminate the gravitational effects that do not depend on density [20], because the effects of density variations are automatically learned by the neural network. All input and output values are linearly scaled in the range $[0, 1]$ by the min–max method.

The wind-load mapping is formulated using feed-forward networks, where signals propagate forward from the input layer to the output layer units, passing through the hidden layer. Indeed, this type of network generally performs well in non-linear regression problems, such as the present one. Training was performed using the resilient backpropagation algorithm (RPROP) [39] with weight-backtracking, as implemented in the neuralnet library [40]. The error function is defined as the squared difference between the estimated and measured wind parameters, i.e.

$$E(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\theta_{E_i}(\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{x}_{M_i}) - \theta_{M_i})^2. \tag{16}$$

The gradient descent technique for back propagation updates the unknown network weights based on the partial derivatives $\partial E / \partial \mathbf{p}$. Specifically, the weights are updated based on the behavior of the sequence of signs of the partial derivatives in each dimension of the weight-space. Therefore, when compared to conventional gradient-descent algorithms, RPROP can reduce the learning steps and convergence time, while providing robustness to different choices of initial values. For further details on this training algorithm, the interested reader is referred to [39].

In principle, it would be possible to train a single network to estimate all wind states in θ . However, as previously argued, this approach would necessitate of the knowledge of all four quantities, a requirement that is often difficult to achieve in practice in the field. Since this is in fact one of the very limits of the legacy approach

Fig. 2. Graphical representation of the NN-based wind observer architecture: each single wind state in $\theta = \{\bar{v}, \kappa_v, \bar{w}, \kappa_h\}^T$ is estimated by a dedicated network based on measured load harmonics; wind speed V and air density ρ schedule the behavior according to the ambient conditions.

described in Section 2.3.1, the single-output network of Fig. 2 was preferred here.

The classical flapwise and edgewise dynamic blade model indicates that only 1P harmonics should be present in the response when the inflow is parameterized as in Eqs. (5). However, due to the approximate nature of the model, one can in reality expect also the presence of higher order terms. To test whether the inclusion of extra terms might improve the results, 2P harmonics were also included within the input signals. Results obtained in a synthetic simulation environment, where the ground truth wind field is known, did not exhibit any improved behavior; actually, at the higher turbulence intensity levels, accuracy was worse than when using only 1P harmonics. These results, not reported here for brevity, confirm what was already reported in Bertelè et al. [17].

A probable explanation of these poor results is as follows. As shown by the analytical derivations of the blade model, higher order response harmonics are driven by correspondingly higher order terms in the expansion of the inflow. If these higher order inflow terms are not considered (which is the present case), higher order harmonics cannot express their presence in the higher inflow modes that drive them and, consequently, they end up polluting the modes that are present, i.e. the four wind parameters $\theta = \{\bar{v}, \kappa_v, \bar{w}, \kappa_h\}^T$. To conclude, including higher-order load harmonics, unless they are accompanied by corresponding higher-order inflow quantities, does not improve the results, and actually produces some pollution of the 1P-driven wind parameters.

3. Results

3.1. Simulation environment

The proposed approach was first tested using a simulated horizontal-axis three-bladed 3 MW wind turbine. The machine has a rotor diameter of 93 m; a hub height of 80 m; 4.5° of nacelle up tilt; and cut-in, rated and cut-out speeds equal to 3, 12.5 and 25 m s⁻¹, respectively. A transition region II 1/2 connects the partial and full-load regimes, extending between 9 and 12.5 m s⁻¹. Simulations were conducted with the aeroservoelastic multibody software Cp–Lambda [41], which is based on a geometrically exact finite element formulation. The model accounts for flexible blades, tower and drive train, and compliant foundations. The collective pitch and torque controller is implemented according to Riboldi [42] and Bottasso et al. [43], while generator and pitch actuators are modeled as first- and second-order dynamical systems, respectively. The aerodynamic rotor model is based on the

Table 1

Values of rotor effective wind speed, TI, density, yaw misalignment, vertical shear, upflow angle and horizontal shear for the whole training and verification dataset.

V [m s ⁻¹]	TI [%]	ρ [kg m ⁻³]	ϕ [°]	κ_v [-]	χ [°]	κ_h [-]
[4, 7, 9, 11, 15, 17]	[5, 12]	1.225	12.00	0.122	4.00	0.000
Same	Same	Same	-10.00	0.060	0.00	0.000
Same	Same	Same	4.00	0.122	12.00	0.000
Same	Same	Same	6.00	0.240	6.00	0.000

Table 2

Minimum and maximum values of rotor effective wind speed, TI, density, yaw misalignment, vertical shear, upflow angle and horizontal shear within the training dataset.

	V [m s ⁻¹]	TI [%]	ρ [kg m ⁻³]	ϕ [°]	κ_v [-]	χ [°]	κ_h [-]
min	3.9	5	1.225	-10.87	-0.022	-0.39	-0.077
max	17.1	5	1.225	12.71	0.300	12.37	0.070

blade element momentum theory (BEM), comprising also classical tip and root losses, unsteady aerodynamics and a dynamic stall model.

Turbulent 10-min-long wind time histories were generated with TurbSim [44] in accordance with the Kaimal model, for the combinations of ambient conditions reported in Table 1, including six wind speeds, two turbulence intensities, and one air density. For each value of wind speed, density and TI, the four different mean inflows of Table 1 were simulated. In addition, to obtain statistically relevant results, 4 different turbulent seeds were considered for each inflow condition, resulting in a total of 192 10-min-long turbulent simulations. The measured wind states, used for model training in Eq. (10) and (16), were derived by linear best-fitting to the rotor swept area the instantaneous wind field at the grid nodes. The corresponding loads were measured on the aeroelastic model by placing sensors at the blade roots. This way, a large dataset of wind states and associated load harmonics was generated at a frequency of 10 Hz.

Both the legacy and the NN models were trained using the same sub-set of the data generated in the simulations. In particular, training was based on one single seed per wind speed at the sole TI level of 5%; this accounts for about 3.6% of the available data. All the rest of the data was used for performance verification. The range covered by each parameter within the training dataset is reported in Table 2.

3.1.1. Observer performance

To find the optimal architecture for each network, the performance was first evaluated as a function of the number of units M in the hidden layer and of the training convergence tolerance. As defined in the `neuralnet` package [40], this tolerance defines the threshold for the partial derivatives of the error function, and is used as stopping criterion for training along with the number of epochs (defined as the number of training cycles in which the algorithm sees the entire identification dataset). While the number of units did not appear to play a significant role, it was found that a stricter convergence tolerance leads to an improved accuracy. This study resulted in the choice of 50 units in the hidden layer and of a 0.1 convergence tolerance.

Fig. 3 shows excerpts of the predictions of each NN, one per subplot, at 9 m s⁻¹ and 5% TI. The solid black lines represent the ground truth derived from the turbulent grid, whereas the red dashed lines represent the estimates. The figures show how the networks accurately follow the instantaneous variations of both shears (Fig. 3b and d); on the other hand, the angles exhibit somewhat larger fluctuations, although the mean values are identified correctly (Fig. 3a and c). This difference in accuracy is simply due to the physics of the problem at hand: to create a same given angle of attack change at a blade section, it takes a larger in-plane speed change (caused by a misalignment angle) than an out-of-plane speed change (caused by a sheared inflow). Because of this, load-based observers are more sensitive to shears than to misalignment angles [17].

Turbulent wind time histories were generated with TurbSim for constant mean values of the shears and angles, according to Table 1. Therefore, the variations observed in the figures are the ones exclusively caused by the underlying turbulence model (Kaimal, in this case); it appears that such model generates significant excursions of the rotor-equivalent shears, but only very modest variations of the rotor-equivalent angles. This limitation of the simulation environment provides further motivation to test the method in more realistic conditions using field test data, as shown later in Section 3.2.

Fig. 4 shows the results obtained at a higher TI level, equal to 12%. As expected, it appears that the higher turbulence leads to larger errors, especially in the angles, as more precisely shown later. Similar results were obtained with the legacy formulation by Bertelè et al. [17].

A more general overview of the NN performance for low (5%) and high (12%) turbulent conditions is presented in Fig. 5. The figure reports on the x axis the 10-min average reference yaw misalignment (a), vertical shear (b) and upflow angle (c), while the respective estimated quantities are plotted along the y axis. No figure is provided for the horizontal shear, because while TurbSim can generate instantaneous horizontal shears due to turbulent fluctuations, it does not allow one to define different mean values for this parameter. The reference quantities show clustering around the nominal inflow values (see Table 1). Note that for the reference shear (Fig. 5b), the 10-min averages exhibit a small scatter. This is due to the Kaimal model implemented in TurbSim: over 10 min, while rotor-equivalent inflow angle variations average out to their nominal value, rotor-equivalent shear fluctuations do not, producing the behavior observed in the plot.

Different colors are used to distinguish low/high wind speeds from intermediate ones, while different symbols distinguish low from high TI cases. In general, as expected, the error is smaller for the lower TI conditions, as already observed in time history plots. Outliers are present for the upflow angle, for some low and high wind speeds where the network extrapolated outside of its training boundaries. For all wind states, the Pearson's correlation coefficient is equal to about 0.99, with only small mean average errors.

Next, results are presented in the form of mean absolute errors (MAE), defined as $\epsilon = 1/N \sum_i^N |\theta_{R_i} - \theta_{E_i}|$, where θ is one of the four wind parameters, subscript $(\cdot)_E$ indicates an estimated value and subscript $(\cdot)_R$ its corresponding reference quantity, while $(\cdot)_i$ indicates one of the N available time samples. Each subplot in Fig. 6, one per wind state, reports a MAE as a function of wind speed and turbulence intensity for both the NN and legacy approaches. Since for the same wind speed and turbulence level different mean inflows and turbulent seeds were considered, each marker in the figure represents the average MAE over 12 10-min-long simulations.

Away from the boundaries of the training set, which are equal to about 4 and 17 m s⁻¹, the two methods behave very similarly: for the lower TI, errors are around 1° and 0.005 for the angles and shears, respectively, while for the higher TI the same errors grow to about 2° and 0.01. This shows that indeed the decoupling of the wind states is possible, and each wind characteristic can be estimated independently from the others, which was one of the main motivations behind this work. A difference between the NN and legacy results is noted for the lowest and highest wind speed values. The reason for this behavior was traced back to the highly nonlinear nature of the NN model. In fact, when operating at the boundaries of the training set, it may happen that the model has to extrapolate outside of the values used for training. For the linear legacy model, this leads to relatively modest errors, whereas much larger ones can be generated in the same conditions by the NN model. The danger of extrapolating using NNs shown by these results was duly taken into account when using field data, by using a wide enough training set. In fact, as shown later in Section 3.2, when extrapolations are avoided, the NN actually behaves slightly better than the legacy approach, especially at the lowest wind speeds.

Fig. 3. Estimates of the wind states in turbulent wind conditions at 9 m s^{-1} and 5% TI. Solid thick black lines: reference wind parameters; dashed thick red lines: NN observations.

Fig. 4. Estimates of the wind states in turbulent wind conditions at 9 m s^{-1} and 12% TI. Solid thick black lines: reference wind parameters; dashed thick red lines: NN observations.

Fig. 5. Correlation of 10 min averages between estimated parameters (y axis) and their reference quantities (x axis). Orange color: $V \in [5, 15.5] \text{ m s}^{-1}$; blue color: $V < 5$ and $V > 15.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$; circles: 5% TI; squares: 12% TI. Yaw misalignment angle (a); vertical linear shear (b); upflow angle (c). Black solid line: ideal match; R: Pearson's correlation coefficient; N: number of data points; MAE: mean absolute error; RMSE: root mean square error.

Fig. 6. MAE ϵ vs. wind speed for 5% and 12% TI: yaw misalignment (a); vertical shear (b); upflow angle (c); horizontal shear (d). Solid blue line: NN model; dashed red line: legacy model; circles: 5% TI; squares: 12% TI.

3.2. Field testing

3.2.1. Test site

After a first verification in a simulated environment, the performance of the proposed neural-based observer was tested using field data. Fig. 7 shows a satellite view of the test site [45], which is located near Brusow, Germany, a few kilometers inland from the Baltic Sea, and is characterized by gentle hills, open fields and forests.

Data was collected between October 19 and November 29, 2017 on a 3.5 MW eno114 turbine designed and produced by eno energy systems GmbH (labeled WT1 in Fig. 7). The turbine has a 92 m hub height and a rotor radius of 114.9 m, and it is equipped with strain gauges installed at the root of two of its three blades, measuring both flapwise and edgewise moment components.

A met mast is situated at about 2.5 diameters (D) from the turbine. The wind direction was measured at a height above ground of 89.3 m with a Thies GmbH wind anemometer, while wind speed measurements were obtained with three cup anemometers produced by the same company and located at 89.3 m, 91.5 m and at the lower tip of the rotor (about 34 m). All measurements from the mast were shifted in time on account of its distance from the turbine, the time delay being computed from the average wind speed.

The mast, turbine and blade loads measurements were sampled at 10 Hz, and were corrected for inconsistencies as explained in Schreiber et al. [11] and Bertelè et al. [20].

A second turbine (labeled WT2) is also present at the site, and its wake affects the met mast and WT1 for easterly and southeasterly winds. Similarly, the wake of WT1 shades the met mast for northern wind directions. To avoid these effects, the training set was limited to the wind directions $\Gamma \in [180, 340]^\circ$. A high roughness area east of WT1, caused by a forest of 15–20 m tall trees, is outside of this sector. On the other hand, some unidentified effects might be caused by the town of Brusow, which is located about 1 km to the west of the site. A previous test campaign conducted at the same site in the period July–November 2016 showed an almost equal distribution of unstable, neutral and stable conditions, as measured by an eddy covariance station [45].

3.2.2. Network identification

In order to train and then validate the NNs, the model inputs and outputs must first be derived from the field measurements.

The rotor-effective wind speed was estimated via the torque balance equation [8–10], using a FAST [46] model of the machine and the measured wind turbine power. Another wind estimator, called Sector Effective Wind Speed (SEWS) observer, was used to derive the rotor-effective vertical and horizontal shears. In synthesis, the method works by first mapping loads measured on each blade into local estimates of the wind speed, and then averaging the resulting signals over the four (top, right, bottom, and left) rotor quadrants. These four wind estimates can be used to reconstruct the vertical and horizontal shears over the rotor disk. The SEWS observer was used because the met mast reaches only to hub height, and therefore a method is needed to extend the vertical shear to the top of the rotor. Training a rotor effective shear estimator with a shear measured only up to hub height is not recommended, because shear often changes with height above ground. Schreiber et al. [11] provides additional details on the SEWS formulation, reports the results of its verification at this very same site, and explains in detail the reconstruction of the shear over the whole rotor.

The experimental setup did not allow to estimate rotor-effective angles. The yaw misalignment was derived by subtracting the nacelle orientation from the wind direction recorded by the mast at hub height. The upflow angle was assumed to be equal to the rotor up tilt, as no relevant orographic effects are expected on this relatively flat terrain.

Air density was derived from the ambient temperature, based on the ideal gas law. Blade harmonics were computed by the Coleman–Feingold transformation [33], after reconstructing the missing flap and edgewise moments on blade 2 by shifting and averaging the signals of blades 1 and 3 [20].

The NNs were trained using 10-min means of the original 10 Hz data streams, in order to average out the effect of possible outliers and to mimic the standard format of SCADA data. About 60% of the available data was used for identification, leaving about 140 h of 10 Hz measurements for validation. Training datasets of different sizes were also considered, showing a slight increase in performance for the larger dataset, which is the one considered in this work. Table 3 shows the range covered by each parameter within the training dataset.

Significant limitations of the experimental setup prevent a real field validation of the proposed methodology: first, there is no rotor-effective measurement of the yaw misalignment; second, and more importantly, the rotor-effective shears are based on another observer, which is based on the same load signals. This observer is validated with respect to

Fig. 7. Satellite view of the test site, including yawing directions and distances. WT1 indicates the turbine used for the present analysis (© Google Maps).

Table 3

Minimum and maximum values of rotor effective wind speed, TI, density, yaw misalignment, vertical and horizontal shear within the training dataset.

	V [m s^{-1}]	TI [%]	ρ [kg m^{-3}]	ϕ_{MM} [$^{\circ}$]	κ_v [-]	κ_h [-]
min	3.50	0.43	1.20	-12.66	-0.045	-0.076
max	19.31	17.29	1.27	8.28	0.312	0.087

the met mast, but only up to hub height [11]. Keeping in mind these limitations, the following results provide a first proof of concept of the proposed formulation, and a partial assessment of its performance in a realistic setting.

3.2.3. Observer performance

First, similarly to the simulation study, the effects of a different number of hidden-layer neurons and of a stricter or looser convergence tolerance were analyzed. Here again, the performance of the NNs did not appear to be particularly affected by the number of units, resulting in the choice of 75 neurons. On the other hand, tests indicate that shears benefit from tighter tolerances than angles. This is probably due to the fact that, as previously noted in Section 3.1.1, the observation of shears is typically more precise than the observation of angles. Based on tests, the convergence tolerance was set to 0.01 for the shears, and to 0.1 for the angles.

A first overview of the results is given by Fig. 8 in terms of 10 min averages, where the estimated yaw misalignment, vertical and horizontal shears are shown as functions of the respective references, the bisector representing the ideal match. The accuracy of the shear estimates is quite high, with root mean square errors (RMSE) of the order of 10^{-3} and Pearson coefficients between 0.98 and 0.99. As expected, the correlation of the yaw misalignment is not as good (0.83), but the RMSE of 1.7° is considerably low. It should be noted that the reference yaw misalignment is provided by the met mast, which, being located about 2.5 D from the rotor and measuring a point-wise value, can hardly represent an exact ground truth. Additionally, measurements at the same site with a more complete setup including a lidar profiler reported significant veer of the inflow [45].

Interestingly, although the NNs were trained starting from 10 min averages, they can still provide time-resolved estimates of the parameters. Fig. 9 shows an exemplary time history sampled at 10 Hz for the yaw misalignment (a), vertical (b) and horizontal (c) shears. As already noted, the shear estimates are quite accurate, with a good match of both instantaneous fluctuations and global trends. As far as the yaw

misalignment is concerned, although some minor deviations from the reference (black line) are present, the main variations over time are well captured by the observer (red line).

To obtain more statistically relevant results, the data in the validation set was analyzed in terms of 10 min averages and then binned as a function of the most relevant parameters. Fig. 10 shows the MAE for the yaw angle (a), vertical (b) and horizontal (c) shear as functions of binned wind speed and rotor effective TI. Fig. 10d shows the available hours present in each bin in the form of an histogram. Looking first at the yaw misalignment, it appears that the MAE between the NN estimated angle and the mast reference is on average around 1–2°, with an increasing accuracy at the higher wind speeds. Moreover, turbulence does not seem to have a significant effect on the results. Looking now at the vertical shear, Fig. 10b reports the MAE as the sum of the NN and SEWS estimation errors. Even including the SEWS estimation error (i.e. the error of the SEWS observer with respect to the mast [11]), the MAE remains quite small, with a mild loss in accuracy for higher TI. Fig. 10c reports the horizontal shear, whose error – although very small – might not be very indicative: since no reference value was available from the met mast for this quantity, only the error with respect to the SEWS observer could be quantified.

Another relevant parameter for the performance analysis is air density. Fig. 11 reports the results for varying density, expressed as percent change with respect to the reference value of 1.238 kg m^{-3} . All plots, again one per parameter, show that density variations up to 5% do not significantly affect the results, which is not surprising given that air density is one of the NN inputs. Indeed, providing density directly as an input to the NN removes the need for the complex density corrections required by the previously published legacy model formulation [20].

To conclude the analysis, the performance of the new proposed NN method was compared to the one of the legacy formulation. For this purpose, the model already identified and validated in Bertelè et al. [20] was used to estimate once again the wind parameters of this new validation set. This legacy model was identified exploiting the rotational symmetry and using only 15% of the available data, which is considerably less than the 60% required for the NNs training. Despite the different identification datasets, the model of Bertelè et al. [20] was chosen for the comparison, since it represents the state of the art version of the legacy model: an accurate and robust observer that can be easily identified, since it requires only a few useful days of data for training. Fig. 12 shows the MAE for each parameter as a function of wind speed, this time both for the NN model (solid blue line) and for

Fig. 8. Correlation of 10 min averages between estimated parameters (y axis) and their reference quantities (x axis) for $V \geq 8 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Yaw misalignment angle (a); vertical linear shear (b); horizontal linear shear (c). Red dashed line: linear best fit; black dashed line: ideal match; R : Pearson’s correlation coefficient; N : number of data points; MAE: mean absolute error; RMSE: root mean square error.

Fig. 9. Field observations at 10Hz of yaw misalignment (a), vertical (b) and horizontal shear (c). Black: reference quantities; red: NN estimates.

Fig. 10. MAE ϵ vs. binned rotor-effective wind speed, for binned TI. Yaw misalignment (a); vertical shear (b); horizontal shear (c); hours of available data (d).

Fig. 11. MAE ϵ vs. binned rotor-effective wind speed, for binned density change $\Delta\rho$ with respect to the mean air density recorded at the site. Yaw misalignment (a); vertical shear (b); horizontal shear (c); hours of available data (d).

Fig. 12. MAE ϵ vs. binned rotor-effective wind speed. Blue solid line: NN model; dashed red line: legacy model. Yaw misalignment (a); vertical shear (b); horizontal shear (c); hours of available data (d).

the legacy one (dashed red line). The performance is in general very similar between the two methods, with some advantage of the NN over the legacy approach at the lower wind speeds for the yaw misalignment and the vertical shear. This may be due to the linear nature of the legacy model, which cannot accurately map this very low wind speed region. Indeed, simulations studies, not reported here for the sake of brevity, show a more pronounced nonlinear behavior in the wind-load map close to cut-in speed.

4. Conclusions

This paper has presented a novel formulation of a previously published wind sensing technology that estimates the rotor-effective inflow based on the lowest harmonic response of the rotor. Specifically, the piecewise-linear load-wind model at the heart of the previous formulation was replaced here by independent feed-forward neural networks, each one mapping directly load harmonics into a wind parameter. Once trained, the neural-based observer is capable of estimating characteristics of the rotor inflow in real time during operation of the turbine, directly from measured rotor loads.

The performance of the new proposed formulation was first tested in a simulation environment, and then in the field using an existing

dataset. Based on the results obtained in this study, the following conclusions and comparisons between the two methods can be made:

- Individual networks can be trained to estimate each one of four wind states (two shears and two angles) independently from the others. This simplifies the training compared to the previous formulation when not all wind parameters can be measured, which is often the case in practical applications. Additionally, a low quality of one or more of the measured parameters cannot affect the accuracy of the estimates of the other parameters. This problem was partially mitigated in the legacy method by exploiting the axial symmetry of the response. In principle this should be possible also for the new approach, where a vertical shear observer is first trained and then used also for observing horizontal shears (and the same for the angles); this possible improvement was however not yet attempted here, and might be the subject of future work.
- The networks can accurately estimate the vertical shear, with a mean error in general close to 0.01 with respect to the mast. Although the horizontal shear could not be validated for the lack of a reference, a similar quality can be expected also for this quantity, as the method and the driving inputs are the same.

Vertical linear shears up to 0.3 were commonly encountered in the experimental dataset, while [11] reported horizontal linear shears up to about 0.45 in waking conditions. The accuracy of the observer seems sufficient for capturing stability changes in the atmosphere [29], which are relevant for wind farm control due to their effects of wake behavior, and for wake detection, which is also relevant for wind farm control.

- The mean yaw misalignment is estimated with average absolute errors in general between 1 and 2°. Such an accuracy should be sufficient for yaw control, and compares favorably with sophisticated anemometry based on spinner-mounted sonic sensors [47].
- Overall, the new formulation has an accuracy that is very similar to the one of the previously published method, with only minor improvements for the lower wind speed ranges. A possible issue with the new neural-based formulation was found close to the boundaries of the training dataset: extrapolating outside of the training range can lead to large errors, probably because of the high nonlinearities of the neural activation functions. The legacy piecewise-linear model appears to be less sensitive to this problem.
- No matter if trained with 10 Hz time histories or with 10 min averages, the networks appear able to follow relatively fast fluctuations in the shears (see Fig. 9 for an example). For applications with fast frequencies, the method of Bertelè and Bottasso [22] could be applied to the new NN-based observer, to approximately compensate the lack of dynamic effects in the load-wind model.
- The formulation is robust to changes in ambient density, thanks to the fact that density itself is used as an input parameter of the NNs. This simplifies the use of the method, as the more complex density corrections required by the previous formulation become unnecessary.
- Field results did not seem to be particularly influenced by turbulence intensity, in contrast to the findings of the simulation study. A larger number of field testing hours might be needed to draw more definitive conclusions.

This work was based on the same field data already used by Schreiber et al. [11] and Bertelè et al. [20]. As also noted in these two papers, the dataset and experimental setup present various limitations that prevented a thorough validation. Therefore, additional tests, possibly based on rotor-effective measurements of both shears and misalignments such as those provided by lidars, would be necessary to perform a more complete validation. In addition, the question of whether this methodology is turbine-type-specific but not pad-specific (i.e. it can be trained on a turbine model and then used on different installations of that same type) still remains open. Notwithstanding these limits, the results obtained so far seem promising, and motivate further efforts towards a more complete understanding of the capabilities of this class of methods.

Nomenclature

H	Height of the hub above ground
m	Blade bending moment
\mathbf{m}	Vector of moment harmonics
M	Number of hidden neurons
N	Number of available data points
R	Rotor radius or Pearson’s coefficient
\mathbf{Q}	Covariance matrix
V	Wind speed
u, v, w	Wind speed components in nacelle-attached frame
x, y, z	Hub-centered nacelle-attached axes
ϵ	Mean absolute error
θ	Wind state vector
κ_h	Horizontal shear

κ_v	Vertical shear
ρ	Air density
ϕ	Yaw misalignment angle
χ	Upflow angle
$\mathbf{E}[\cdot]$	Expected value operator
$\text{NN}[\cdot]$	Neural network function
$\tilde{(\cdot)}$	Non-dimensional quantity
$(\cdot)^T$	Transpose
$(\cdot)^{\text{IP}}$	In-plane component
$(\cdot)^{\text{OP}}$	Out-of-plane component
$(\cdot)_{1c}$	1P cosine amplitude
$(\cdot)_{1s}$	1P sine amplitude
$(\cdot)_E$	Estimated quantity
$(\cdot)_H$	Hub-height quantity
$(\cdot)_M$	Measured quantity
$(\cdot)_R$	Reference quantity
$(\cdot)_{\text{RMS}}$	Root mean square
1P	Once per revolution
BEM	Blade element momentum
MAE	Mean absolute error
NN	Neural network
RMS	Root mean square
SEWS	Sector-effective wind speed
TI	Turbulence intensity
WT	Wind turbine

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kwang-Ho Kim: Methodology, Software, Validation. **Marta Bertelè:** Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Carlo L. Bottasso:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their gratitude to Stefan Bockholt and Alexander Gerds of eno energy systems GmbH, who granted access to the measurement data and turbine model, and to Marijn van Dooren, Anantha Sekar and Martin Kühn of ForWind Oldenburg, who shared insight on the data.

Financial support

This work has been supported by the CompactWind II project (FKZ: 0325492G), which receives funding from the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK), and by a research grant from Kangwon National University, Republic of Korea in 2019. Additional funding was provided by the European Union under the Horizon Europe grant No. 101084216 (project MERIDIONAL).

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